

EOSC-IF

Guidance note: Reviewing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework

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EOSC-IF / Guidance note: Reviewing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework

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Dissemination Level of the Document

Public

Abstract

This document is for members of the reviewing panel for Interoperability Guidelines that have been submitted for consideration of inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework's Registry.

This document gives a short overview of the process and provides links to useful resources to help reviewers of guidelines.

It is for the use of members of the IF Guideline Review meetings.

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
V0.1	April 2023	Authored by Michelle Williams (GÉANT), Anke Friedrich (GÉANT)	First draft for review by EOSC Future WP3 Participants
V0.2	April 2023	Daan Broeder (CLARIN), Gavin Farrell (ELIXIR/EMBL)	Comments provided
V1.0	May 2023	Michelle Williams (GÉANT), Anke Friedrich (GÉANT)	Final Version published to Zenodo

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Glossary

EOSC Future project Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JQCK>

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
EIAC	EOSC Interoperability Area Chairs
EOSC-IF	EOSC Interoperability Framework
EPOT	EOSC Portal Onboarding Team
FQDN	Fully Qualified Domain Names
PID	Persistent Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

1 Introduction

The EOSC-IF will be built upon a wide range of components, such as standards, APIs, policy frameworks, etc. Starting with human-readable interoperability guidelines that aim to promote and facilitate interoperability across services, resources, infrastructures and domains, the Framework will begin to incorporate more executable, machine-readable artefacts that would support composable or executable workflows at a later stage. Guidance is offered to reviewers of Interoperability Guidelines.

It is assumed that Interoperability Guidelines will be already established and published by an Infrastructure or Scientific Domain/Community, and, therefore, an author will not intend to write a new Interoperability Guideline for submission to the EOSC Interoperability Framework. However, it is conceivable that an existing Interoperability Guideline or collection of Guidelines would benefit from being structured into an EOSC Interoperability Guideline. In this case, a Word template has been provided¹ that is tailored towards Interoperability Guidelines produced under the EOSC Future project, but that can also be utilised (ensuring that the relevant copyright and project funding statements are updated as required), and the following guidance notes can be utilised in producing that document.

More information can be found at:

[Interoperability Framework Governance](#)
[EIAB and EIAC Charter](#)
<https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-interoperability-framework/>

2 The Role of the Reviewer

- To perform the common checks within the allotted time.
- To support or deny the proposal, based on the outcome of its review and to provide feedback during the procedure.

3 Common Checks

The following checks should be taken into consideration when reviewing an Interoperability Guideline for inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework:

Does the proposed Guideline meet the Inclusion Criteria ² ?	Interoperability Guidelines must be reviewed in the context that they are expected to meet the following inclusion criteria: https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria#EOSCExchangeinclusioncriteria-3.6.Additionalinclusioncriteria toonboardaninteroperabilityguideline . This will be uploaded to https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-providers-hub	See below
The guideline's documentation and description (i.e. the metadata defined by the Provider) is actively maintained.		Y/N/Partially

¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-interoperability-framework/eosc-if-templates-and-information>

² EOSC Onboarding Inclusion Criteria, [online] Available at:
<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria>

<p>The Guideline is published at a well-supported, commonly used and open public repository, and that repository is capable of version control for future versions of the documentation or software.</p>	<p>e.g. Zenodo</p>	<p>Y/N/Partially</p>
<p>The Guideline has been assigned a PID.</p>		<p>Y/N/Partially</p>
<p>There is evidence that the described interoperability has been demonstrated in a relevant environment.</p>		<p>Y/N/Partially</p>
<p>It is evident that the guideline is mature, meaning that it is version 1+, or higher, that it is actively maintained and/or that it has evidenced uptake.</p>	<p>This refers to at least part of the available software (necessary for) implementing the guideline and that it includes adequate support documentation, and, where a document is obviously in a draft state, it should not be considered ready for proposal to the Registry.</p>	<p>Y/N/Partially</p>
<p>Does the guideline comprise the minimum required information as specified in the templates found at https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-interoperability-framework/?</p>	<p>Note that Authors are encouraged to use the following templates: https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-interoperability-framework/eosc-if-templates-and-information Authors must take into consideration and adhere to the information given in the template, however, authors are entitled to flex the template to fit their needs, or to use an existing document/template from their own Infrastructure or Community, provided that it does not dilute the quality of the resulting document or result in the omission of key sections of information.</p>	<p>Y/N/Partially</p>
<p>Does the guideline have a documented and methodical approach to the description of how to implement its recommendations and related software?</p>		<p>Y/N/Partially</p>
<p>Do URLs cited in the guideline documentation or Registry Profile have Fully Qualified Domain Names (FQDN)?</p>	<p>And are those resources publicly accessible?</p>	<p>Y/N/Partially</p>
<p>Is it evident that the guideline has been successfully utilised and proven within the community</p>	<p>Specifically for EOSC-Exchange Interoperability Guidelines (thematic and horizontal interoperability guidelines as defined in the EOSC Glossary).</p>	<p>Y/N/Partially/Not Applicable</p>

concerned? Is further evidence required of that?	This could be evidenced by descriptions of uptake and/or maturity.	
Is it evident that the Guideline has been subject to community consultation and that (partial) community acceptance can be demonstrated?	Specifically for EOSC-Exchange Interoperability Guidelines (thematic and horizontal interoperability guidelines as defined in the EOSC Glossary). This could be evidenced by descriptions of uptake and/or maturity, and ideally a Guideline would already have been formally endorsed by its community.	Y/N/Partially/Not Applicable
Does the proposed Guideline successfully communicate how to achieve interoperability in the given context?	For example, communities will be entitled to publish information describing how they interoperate as a community, and how other communities can interoperate with them. Exposing information to providers and users, will help them to understand more about necessary prerequisites or technical boundaries when interoperating in a specified context. At a lower level of abstraction, a service may specify adoption of particular standards, APIs, protocols, etc, as an underlying requirement to interface with it.	

4 Content and Quality Considerations

Ideally the Guideline would be reusable, and would be a 'recipe for an interoperability solution listing protocols, standards and formats in a machine readable way' (as opposed to a Guideline that promotes only one standard, format, protocol, etc.), that would allow (research) service or workflow implementation with specific interoperability goals in mind, that is, to understand boundary conditions of related services and ecosystems, to establish rules for interoperating at the edges of those boundaries, and to serve ideally as an example for work where interoperability problems have been solved.

Authors or proposers of Interoperability Guidelines should aim to incorporate the following characteristics:

Clear and Concise: The guideline should be easy to follow, using clear and concise language. Authors should take care to ensure the correct level of technical detail is provided and should avoid use of jargon that is difficult for users to understand.

Comprehensive: The guideline should be self-contained by default, covering all relevant aspects of creating or configuring the interoperability solution, including technical standards, protocols, data formats, and interfaces, in order to make it practical and feasible to implement. However, existing widely accepted documentation of standards etc. should be referenced rather than copied.

Adaptable: The guideline should be flexible enough to accommodate changes and updates as new technologies and standards emerge.

Consistent: If the guideline references another, it should be consistent with the referenced guideline with direct references to the relevant version. It should not contradict or replicate the referenced guideline. References/dependencies (and their explicit versions) must be declared in the related standards table.

User-Centred: The guideline should be designed with a specific implementer audience in mind, and should set out clearly the characteristics of that audience.

Well-Tested: The guideline should be well-tested and validated through practical use cases and scenarios.

The provider of an Interoperability Guideline assumes the responsibility to maintain it, in the sense that it should be reviewed and updated throughout its serviceable life when needed.

Where an Interoperability Guideline relates to a workflow, practice, service or software product, the Guideline should be updated in line with the workflow, practice, service or software product update.

Overall, an Interoperability Guideline should provide clear and actionable guidance that helps users achieve interoperability in a consistent and efficient manner.

5 Procedural Context

1. **Proposing a Guideline for Inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework** - Proposer requests inclusion of new guidelines to be included in the EOSC IF; refer to the Guidance Notes on Onboarding a Guideline to the EOSC Interoperability Framework.³This is initiated by the proposer by onboarding a new Interoperability Guideline Profile via the EOSC Providers Portal⁴, which will trigger an Onboarding Procedure via the EPOT channels.
2. **Review procedure** - The topic of this Guidance Note. New requests are reviewed in terms of technical quality and clarity, and are assessed as to whether they are consistent with the expectation of EOSC IF guidelines.
3. **Endorsement procedure** - New guidelines are discussed within the EIAC and, if approved, submitted to the EIAB for endorsement.
4. **Dissemination procedure** - Adopted guidelines are announced via the EOSC channels.

6 Review Procedure

- The EIAC Chair creates an endorsement request page for the guideline on the appropriate wiki (currently <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EIAB+and+EIAC+Charter>) and links the guideline in using its URI starting <https://doi...>
- The EIAC Chair finds volunteer reviewers to appraise the proposed Guideline. This can be achieved either by hosting regular meetings or by requesting volunteers via email to the eiac@eoscfuture.eu mailing list.
- The reviewers examine the quality of the submitted guideline and metadata referring to the Inclusion Criteria, and the general recommendations and guidance set out in the template. This may include spelling, accuracy, composition, and URLs, but the reviewers will not perform interoperability tests as a matter of routine.
- The reviewers write their comments in the appropriate position on the related endorsement page filling in the first four columns of the Comment/Change log.
- During this procedure, the reviewers or the EIAC Chair may request evidence that the Guideline has been verified, and that it is mature within the Infrastructure, Domain or Community that proposed it.
- The authors must reply to any queries, and in some cases may be asked to make changes to the Guideline documentation, and to provide an updated version of the documentation before it can be endorsed.
- The Reviewers fill in the table 'Statements of Support/Deny'.

7 Endorsement Procedure

- Based on the outcome of the Review Procedure, the remaining EIAC members fill in the table 'Statements of Support/Deny'.

³ Guidance note: Onboarding an Interoperability Guideline to EOSC: 10.5281/zenodo.7929834

⁴ <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/home>

- All responses (support/deny) are treated as votes as whether or not to accept the Guideline into the EOSC Interoperability Framework. This may take place either during a 'Interoperability Guideline Review Meeting' or via email.
- The outcome of the vote becomes a recommendation to the EIAB made by the EIAC Chair.
- The EIAB may have additional comments, and will approve or reject the proposed Guideline.
- The EIAC Chair will contact the author/owner to inform them of the outcome.

[end of action for reviewers]

8 Dissemination Procedure (for approved Guidelines)

- The authors make final changes to the guideline and submit the final version to the EIAC Chair.
- EIAC Chair and EPOT team progresses the Onboarding workflow to publish the Guideline's Profile and marks it as 'Accepted'.
- The EIAC Chair informs the EOSC Future Outreach/Communications team that a new Interoperability Guideline is available, and this can be communicated in the next EOSC Future newsletter.

9 EIAC Members (at April 2023):

Name	Deputy	Organisation
George Papastefanatos	Thanassis Mantes, Aggeliki Gkamiliari	ATHENA
Mark Dietrich	none	EGI
Kostas Koumantaros	none	GRNET
Roksana Rozanska	none	Cyfronet
Mark van de Sanden	Jorik van Kemenade, Paul Gondim van Dongen	SURF
Jonathan Tedds	Gavin Farrell	EMBL/ELIXIR
PAOLO MANGHI	Andreas Czerniak, Sabeel Shah, (Pedro Principe)	OpenAIRE
Pavel Weber	none	KIT
Christos Kanellopoulos	none	GEANT
Diego Scardaci	Andrea Manzi, Levente Farkas	EGI

Related documents

- Guidance note: Writing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework: 10.5281/zenodo.7929870
- Guidance note: Onboarding an Interoperability Guideline to EOSC: 10.5281/zenodo.7929834
- EPOT Procedure-14: Onboard an Interoperability Guideline (relating to EPOT team activities).⁵

References

- [1] EOSC Interoperability Framework, online. Available at <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-interoperability-framework/>
- [2] EOSC Interoperability Framework Inclusion Criteria, 2023, online. Available at: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria#EOSCExchangeinclusioncriteria-3.6.Additionalinclusioncriteriatoonboardaninteroperabilityguideline>
- [3] EOSC Providers Portal, online. Available at <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/home>
- [4] EOSC Portal Providers Hub, online. Available at <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-providers-hub>
- [5] EIAC and EIAB Charter, online. Available at <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EIAB+and+EIAC+Charter>

⁵

<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCOB/EPOT+Procedure-14%3A+Onboard+an+Interoperability+Guideline>